

**Extraction-photometric Determination of Iron,
Copper and Chromium using Thioorganic
Reagents**

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*Manuscript received 26 February 1990,
revised 22 February 1991, accepted 20 March 1991*

SEVERAL reagents have been proposed for extraction-photometric determination of iron¹, copper² and chromium^{5,6}. In the investigations of developing new thioreagents from this laboratory¹⁻³, PTTT and PTTSC are now recommended as sensitive reagents for these metals. PTTT has been used for extraction and simultaneous determination of cobalt and nickel⁷. PTTSC⁸ has been used earlier.

Stock solutions of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} were prepared from A. R. grade sulphate of the respective metals and that of Cr^{VI} was prepared from K₂Cr₂O₇. Absorbance measurements were made on a Backman DU-2 spectrophotometer.

Experimental

General procedure :

Iron : To an aliquot of solution containing 25 μg Fe^{II} was added sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer

(10 ml; pH=4.5) and the total volume was made to 20 ml with distilled water. To it was added 0.01% solution (5 ml) of PTTT in acetone and the mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min for colour development. The yellowish coloured complex was extracted in chloroform (5 ml) for 30 s. The organic layer was withdrawn and its absorbance was noted at 420 nm against a reagent blank. Both Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} reacted identically with the reagent.

Copper: To a solution (1 ml) containing 10 µg Cu^{II} was added 1.25 N NaCl solution (10 ml). The total volume was made up to 20 ml with distilled water and its pH was adjusted to 5.0±0.1. A 0.01% PTTT solution (5 ml) in acetone was then added to it and the mixture was allowed to stand for 5 min for colour development. The yellowish coloured complex was extracted with toluene (5 ml) and its absorbance was noted at 420 nm against a reagent blank.

Chromium: To a 10 µg Cr^{VI} solution in a beaker, 0.5 M CH₃COOH (5 ml) was added followed by 0.05% PTTSC solution (5 ml) in acetone. The mixture was kept for 10 min for colour development. The yellowish coloured complex formed was extracted with chloroform (5 ml). The organic layer was withdrawn and its absorbance was noted at 335 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

In all the cases complexation occurs in cold and the complexes are sufficiently stable. Quantitative extraction is obtained for Fe at pH 4.0–5.0, for Cu at pH 3.0–7.0 and 0.04–0.32 M effective concentration of CH₃COOH for Cr. A 0.01% PTTT solution (5 ml) in acetone is sufficient for quantitative extraction of Fe and Cu, and a 0.05% PTTSC solution (5 ml) for quantitative extraction of Cr^{VI}. Toluene, chloroform, benzene and carbon tetrachloride extracts the Fe and Cu complexes quantitatively while the Cr^{VI} complex is extracted quantitatively with chloroform, benzene and n-amyl alcohol. Beer's law is obeyed in the ranges 1.0–7.5 µg for Fe and 0.5–4.5 µg for Cu and Cr. The optimum ranges evaluated from Ringbom plot (µg/ml) are 1.0–7.4, 0.8–4.0 and 0.7–3.7; the values for Sandell's sensitivity are 0.014, 0.006 and 0.004 µg cm⁻²; molar absorptivity (lit. mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) are 4.0×10³, 1.0×10⁴ and 1.3×10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; and relative mean deviation for ten determinations are 0.62, 0.77 and 0.51%, respectively for Fe, Cu and Cr systems.

The following amounts (µg) of foreign ions are found to give less than ±2% error in determination of iron (25 µg), copper (10 µg) and chromium (10 µg) respectively: chloride (625, excess, excess), sulphite (800, 600, 120), thiosulphate (1120 for each), sulphide (320, 640, 640); citrate (1890, 1890, 55), oxalate (880 each), EDTA (interferes, interferes, excess), Mg^{II} (600, 960, 1200), Mn^{II} (825, 1100, 2750), Zn^{II} (650, 650, 3250), Pb^{II} (2070 for each), Cd^{II} (1120, 560, 560), Hg^{II} (200 for each), Cr^{III} (520 for each), Al^{III}

(650, 780, 540), Bi^{III} (1050 for each), Mo^{VI} (300 for each), V^V (200 for each), W^{VI} (300 for each). Interference due to Cu^{II} in iron determination was eliminated by masking it with thiourea.

Cobalt and nickel interfere in the determination of iron and copper. In chromium determination, Cu^{II} and V^V were masked with EDTA, whereas Fe^{III} was masked with pyrophosphate.

Determination of iron in drugs: Iron present in drugs in the form of ferrous sulphate, ferrous succinate and ferrous fumarate can be conveniently determined by this method. For this tablets or capsules containing iron in the form of ferrous sulphate or ferrous succinate were boiled with double-distilled water (70–80 ml) containing concentrated HCl (3–4 drops). The solution was filtered and the residue washed with water and the filters made up to 250 ml. In case of sample containing iron as ferrous fumarate, it was digested with concentrated H₂SO₄ (20 ml) for 2–3 h. The solution was transferred, concentrated to about 1 ml, cooled and diluted with distilled water. In all the cases a solution containing 25 µg of Fe per ml was prepared by suitable dilution and the procedure was followed. To an aliquot of solution containing iron was added acetate buffer (10 ml) of pH 4.5 and the total volume was made up to 20 ml with distilled water. The recommended procedure was then followed. The results obtained were compared with standard o-phenanthroline method. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRON IN DRUGS

Sl. no.	Drug*	Iron per Tab. (mg)**		
		(1)	(2)	Error %
1.	Iberol ^a	105.46	103.25	2.09
2.	Tablets of ferrous of sulphate and folic acid ^b	21.92	21.61	1.41
3.	Ferrous sulphate and compound ^b	61.07	60.20	1.42
4.	Hematrine ^c	32.28	32.00	0.86
5.	Fesofar ^d	55.16	54.28	1.59
6.	Becaudaxamine ^e	16.43	16.06	2.25
7.	Siderfol ^f	88.61	98.50	0.11
8.	Iberol tonic ^a	26.25	28.71	1.75
9.	Compoferon ^g	109.62	107.73	1.72

*Manufacturer: ^aAbott, ^bEupharm3, ^cSandoz, ^dReptakos Brett, ^eGlaxo, ^fSmith, Kline and French, ^gBayer.

** (1) o-Phenanthroline method; (2) Present method.

Determination of copper in alloys: To a weighed sample of Cu (~0.1 g), was added concentrated HNO₃ (10 ml) and the mixture was heated on a sand-bath until the sample dissolved. The solution was evaporated almost to dryness, the residue dissolved in water and the volume was made upto 100 ml and the solution was further diluted with distilled water to a concentration of about 10 µg Cu/ml. The recommended procedure was then followed. The results obtained from 5 determinations compared with

the standard DDC method. In the analysis of the alloy sample-I (certified composition : Cu, 45 ; Al, 50 ; Zn=50%) the present method reports 44.45% copper (DDC method 44.70%) and for the second sample (certified composition : Cu, 92 ; Zn=8%) the present method reports 92.03% copper (DDC method 91.5%). Thus the % errors are 0.25 and 0.53% respectively for two analysed samples.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head of Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, and to Prof. D. G. Wakde, Principal, Shri Sant Gajanan Maharaj Engineering College, Shegaon for encouragement. One of the authors (D.M.A.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship.

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